

Structural Modifications and Geometrical Changes in DNA Quadruple Folding in the Context of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

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Abstract- The four natural DNA bases A-Adenosine, T-Thymine, G-Guanine, C-Cytosine are associated in base pairs as (A=T and G≡C), allowing the attached DNA strands to assemble into the canonical double helix of DNA which is duplex of DNA, also known as B-DNA. The intrinsic supra molecular properties of nucleic bases make other associations possible such as base triplets or quartets, which thus translates into a diversity of DNA structures. The diversity of DNA structures is ripe with approximately 20 letters, (from A- to Z-DNA); however, only a few of them are being considered as key players in cell biology and by extension, valuable targets for chemical biology invention. In the present review, we summarise (1) what is known about alternative DNA structures (2) what are they? (3) When, where and how they fold? These are all proceeded to discuss further and those considered nowadays as valuable therapeutic targets. We discuss in more detail the molecular tools (ligands) that have been recently developed to target these structures. In order to intervene in the biological processes, particularly three and four ways of DNA junctions are involved there. This new and simulating chemical biology playground allows for devising innovative strategies to fight against genetic diseases. For example to find Structural Modification/Geometrical changes by DNA Quadruples Folding are done by attachment of second prototypes of ligands. DNA quadruples participate in many biological functions. It takes up a variety of folds based on the sequence and environment. Here, a meticulous analysis of experimentally determined 437 quadruple structures (433 PDBs) deposited in the PDB is carried out. The analysis reveals the modular representation of the quadruples folds. Forty-eight unique quadruple motifs (whose diversity arises out of the propeller, bulge, diagonal, and lateral loops that connect the quartets) are identified, leading to simple to complex inter/intra molecular quadruple folds. The two-layered structural motifs are further classified into 33 continuous and 15 discontinuous motifs. While the continuous motifs can directly be extended to a quadruple fold; the discontinuous motif requires an additional loop(s) to complete a fold, as illustrated here with examples. Similarly, higher-order quadruple folds can also be represented by continuous or discontinuous motifs or their combinations. In order to achieve Sustainable Development Goals we have to get maximum stable form of folding to get both thermodynamically and kinetically stable DNA or RNA structure to get proper drug design for the treatment of target diseases or cloning purposes. Help of molecular docking software like AutodocVina and help of PDB software we have to perform it. Alternatively applied those drugs to the victim like Rabbits or mouses etc. for a time period for particular target diseases for optimal treatment result conditions. The topic is under the domain of modern Analytical Chemistry and biotechnology up gradation purposes. With attachment of small molecules with DNA/RNA Finding proper cloning or staled DNA folding and to find optimal drug design for the treatment of target disease and to find a diseases free society for lifelong initiatives. Such a modular representation of the quadruple folds may assist in custom engineering of quadruples, designing motif-based drugs, and the prediction of the quadruple structure. Furthermore, it could facilitate understanding of the role of quadruples' in biological functions and diseases

Keywords: DNA/RNA- structure, A to Z- DNA, folding, ligands and target structures, genetic drug design, genetic drug design. Quadruple structure, PDB, Structure generation, drug design.

I. INTRODUCTION

DNA quadruples (G4s) are unique secondary structures formed by guanine-rich DNA or RNA sequences. Unlike the canonical double helix, G4s consist of G-tetrads, which are planar stacks of four guanine bases held together by Hoogsteen hydrogen bonds. These stacks are stabilized by cations such as potassium (K^+) and sodium (Na^+), reducing electrostatic repulsion between guanine residues. G4s exhibit significant structural diversity, with different folding patterns based on strand orientation and loop connectivity. Their presence in key genomic regions, including telomeres, oncogene promoters, and replication origins, underscores their biological relevance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Formation and Stability of G4s

G4s form when guanine-rich nucleic acid sequences fold into planar G-tetrads. The stability of G4s is influenced by, Hoogsteen hydrogen bonds: These form a stable cyclic network between the guanine bases. Cation coordination: K^+ and Na^+ ions reduce electrostatic repulsion, stabilizing the quadruplex. Loop configuration: The structure and length of the connecting loops influence G4 folding and stability. Figure 2: Illustration of G-tetrad formation and stabilization by cations.

Figure 2: Nomenclature of DNA quadruplex folds

with guanine base labeling, G-quartet structures, and hydrogen bonding patterns (SOP).

Structural Diversity and Topologies

G4s adopt different folding patterns based on strand orientation and loop connectivity, categorized as:

- **Parallel quadruplexes:** All strands run in the same direction.
- **Antiparallel quadruplexes:** Alternating strands run in opposite directions.
- **Hybrid quadruplexes:** Combination of parallel and antiparallel strands.

Figure 3: Illustration from SOP showing loop configurations and quadruplex folding patterns.

Structural Motifs and Modularity

Analysis of 437 G4 structures from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) revealed 48 unique motifs, divided into:

- **33 continuous motifs:** These motifs form stable quadruplex folds directly.
- **15 discontinuous motifs:** These require additional loops or linkers to complete the fold.

Biological and Therapeutic Applications

G4s have numerous biological and therapeutic applications:

- **Therapeutic targets:** G4s are promising drug targets for cancer, neurodegenerative disorders, and viral infections.
- **Biomarkers:** The presence of G4s in oncogene promoters makes them reliable biomarkers for cancer diagnosis.

- **Drug design:** G4-targeting molecules are being developed for treating cancer and other diseases.
- **Nanotechnology:** G4s are employed in biosensors, DNA nanowires, and molecular electronics due to their stability and specificity. Future Directions

The modular nature of G4s offers future opportunities:

Custom-engineered G4s for drug delivery and biosensing.

Advanced bioinformatics models for predicting G4 folding patterns.

G4-based nanodevices for sustainable electronics and precision medicine.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

DNA Quadruplex Structures. In order to understand the architecture of various DNA quadruplex folds, the Cartesian coordinates of quadruplex structures were downloaded from PDB,62 NAKB (previously known as NDB),68 and ONQUA- DRO61 using the keyword search "quadruplex", "tetraplex", "tetrad", "quartet", or "G4-helices". After removal of the redundant structures, 437 DNA quadruplexes (433 PDBs as of July 15, 2024) were finally considered for analysis. This includes 11 left-handed structures. Note that the intercalating quadruplex structures (PDB IDs: 1V3P, 2DZ7) (viz., octaplex) are notting microbial transcription through radioresistance, antigenic variation, recombination, and latency.11considered for the analysis as it is beyond the scope of this article.

Deriving Two-Layered Structural Motifs from the DNA Quadruplex Structures. Since the objective of this study is to show that the quadruplex structures or folds are modular in nature in such a way that they can be represented in terms of small repetitive 3D structural units, a thorough analysis of 437 quadruplex PDB structures was carried out in this context. The 3D structural units, henceforth termed quadruplex motifs, were derived from the quadruplex folds by breaking the folds into two-layered structural blocks comprising two quartets. Conformational Angle Preference.

The sugar-phosphate backbone and glycosyl conformational angles [α (O3'-P- O5'-C5'), β (P-O5'-C5'-C4'), γ (O5'-C5'-C4'-C3'), δ (C5'-C4'-C3'-O3'), ϵ (C4'-C3'-O3'-P), ζ (C3'-O3'-P-O5'), and χ (O4'-C1'-N9/N1-C4'/C2')] of each quartet-forming residues in the quadruplex folds (PDBs) were taken from NAKB. The conformational angle preference is reported based on the frequency of occurrence, which is individually normalized with respect to each fold, viz., separately for antiparallel, parallel.

"Quadruple folding by Attachment of small molecule with DNA and RNA."

The primary function of RNA is to create proteins via translation. RNA carries genetic information that is translated by ribosome into various proteins necessary for cellular processes. mRNA, rRNA, and tRNA are the three main types of RNA involved in protein synthesis mRNA (messenger RNA): it provides the template for protein synthesis during translation. tRNA (transfer RNA): it brings amino acids and reads the genetic code during translation. rRNA (ribosomal RNA): it plays a structural and catalytic role during translation.

The four natural RNA bases A-Adenosine ,U-Uracil, G-Guanine, C-Cytosine are associate in base pairs as (A=U and G≡C), allowing the attached DNA strands to assemble into the canonical double helix of RNA which is duplex of RNA, also known as B-RNA. The intrinsic supra molecular properties of nucleo bases make other associations possible such as base triplets or quartets, which thus translates into a diversity of RNA structures is ripe with approximately 20 letters, (from A- to Z-RNA); however, only a few of them are being considered as key players in cell biology and by extension, valuable targets for chemical biology invention. Uracil is replaced by Thymine in case of DNA. In the present review, we summarise (1) what is known about alternative RNA structures (2) what are they? (3)When, where and how they fold?

These are all proceeded to discuss further and those considered nowadays as valuable therapeutic targets. We discuss in more detail the molecular tools (ligands) that have been recently developed to target these structures. In order to intervene in the

biological processes, particularly three and four ways of RNA junctions are involved there. This new and simulating chemical biology playground allows for devising innovative strategies to fight against genetic diseases.

RNA is crucial for gene expression and regulation. Recent advances in understanding of RNA biochemistry, structure and molecular biology have revealed the importance of RNA structure in cellular processes and diseases. Various approaches to discovering drug-like small molecules that target RNA structure have been developed. This review provides a brief introduction to RNA structural biology and how RNA structures function as disease regulators. We summarize approaches to targeting RNA with small molecules and highlight their advantages, shortcomings and therapeutic potential. RNA importance is increasingly appreciated as regulators of human diseases and consequently as potential drug targets. Novel methods to target RNA structure with small molecules rather than RNA sequence have been developed. Knowledge and principles of RNA structure are highly desired to develop more effective RNA structure-targeting drugs.

The four natural DNA bases A-Adenosine, T-Thymine, G-Guanine, C-Cytosine are associate in base pairs as (A=T and G≡C), allowing the attached DNA strands to assemble into the canonical double helix of DNA which is duplex of DNA, also known as B-DNA. The intrinsic supra molecular properties of nucleo bases make other associations possible such as base triplets or quartets, which thus translates into a diversity of DNA structures is ripe with approximately 20 letters, (from A- to Z-DNA); however, only a few of them are being considered as key players in cell biology and by extension, valuable targets for chemical biology invention. In the present review, we summarise (1) what is known about alternative DNA structures (2) what are they? (3)When, where and how they fold?

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The DNA alphabet is naturally restricted to four letters, i.e. A for adenine, C for cytosine, G for guanine and T for thymine (1,2) (although some creative scientists have achieved the juggling act to expand it to 6 in living semi synthetic organisms (3,4), and then 8 (5), mimicking what was discovered in bacterio phages >4 decades ago) (6–9). In contrast, the DNA structure alphabet is far richer, with >20 letters used to date as descriptors of secondary structures). The canonical, so called Watson–Crick, structure is referred to as B-DNA (as the X-ray crystallographic structure was obtained by Rosalind Franklin after hydration of a first sample ('A') of high-quality DNA provided by Rudolf categorized as a non-B-DNA structure, spanning from A-DNA (thus, dehydrated duplex) (11) to Z-DNA (duplex of inverted helicity, Z for zigzag) (10,15).

The central dogma of biology, heralded by Francis Crick in 1957 (16,17), has placed the B-DNA at the very Centre of all molecular biology efforts invested, and discoveries made, after the elucidation of its double helix structure (2,13,18). This has kept the limelight away from reports published in succeeding years on the ability of DNA to fold into a variety of non-B-DNA structures (Figure 1), including: the triple helix (or triplex (19), termed H-DNA given its homo purine (hPu)/homo pyrimidine (hPy) nature, also refer- ring to hinged DNA) (20), first identified in RNA in 1957(21) before being characterized in DNA in 1979; (22) the G-quartet in 1962 (23), the constitutive unit of the quadruple helix G-quadruple (G4-DNA, or G-DNA) whose formation was demonstrated in 1988; (24) the tetra-stranded four-way DNA junction proposed as a model to explain gene conversion in 1964 by Robin Holliday (consequently called the Holliday junction) (25), predicted in 1966 (26) and demonstrated in vitro (and termed cruciform DNA, C- DNA) in the early 80s; (27,28) the Z-DNA first detected in 1967 (as a B-

DNA of inverted, left-handed helicity) (29) before being firmly confirmed in 1979 (30), etc.

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

Methodology in terms of Systematic Review and Literature Review in broad aspect:

As per the above available primary data of the research I have searched DNA/RNA Structure in the Mendeley search Engine, here I have found more than 99000 papers. To minimize and to get best result I have changed the searched words into various option, where only journal papers and Thesis from year 2020 to 2024, which give me best results and was shorten the work into nearly 29032 papers in that searching date 25/11/2023.

Out of this finding the attachments of small molecules shorten to nearly 7292 open access journal papers papers which shorten to m I have made a link of nearly 200 papers in the Mendely Reference Management Software where a prior registration with my email account was done. After that I have made an Excel Sheet where searching tools, paper name, Authors, Abstracts, volume, issue date, Key words, URL, Conclusion etc. data were tabulated. Apart from that Departmental library/central Library books also help me in this review work. But systematic review is done with the help of the mentioned software. It is true the available data are different in different date and time. To get best result it should be carried out in the same date with searching tools and words etc. Some basic steps has been followed to carry out this systematic review of this available primary data on the taken topic and basic ideas.

First in this systematic review process I have searched on the topic of (a) coral reef zone in India. (b) The cause of bleaching process there. With the help of various searching engine I have found the best available papers or book on it. Here the following process has been described in the term of systematic Review. Total no of shorted papers in the excel sheet is 200.

Different Searching results: (14)

(1) Screening: From Scopus-Elsevier searching using key words as "DNA/RNA structure, searching date 25/11/2022, total findings was 29038 for at any time, since 2020 total findings minimizes as 7292, where only open access journals.

(2) Screening: small molecules attachments Elsevier.com results nearly 200, changing key words "attachments with small molecules with DNA/RNA" results only 350 available for open access papers.

(3) 3rd Screening: Changing date 23/12/2023 time 11.35A.M using key words" coral bleaching and India" from Elsevier, all results as 200 where Web page: 73, Books: 45, Journals: 102, thesis: remaining

(4). 4th Screening: Changing key words as in the same Elsevier in the same date "cloning of DNA, results nearly same

(5). 5th Screening: Changing key words as in the published journal: 200,

(6). screening: Changing the key words DNA replication also going through abstract suggested papers result same.

Systematic Review is done in the Excel Sheet, where the 56 papers data are inputted in tabular form. Some of papers which has been carried out there are representing in tabular form in word format in below. The data in tabular form helps us to get best results on research work progress on the above topic. Various graphical representation or charts could be drawn. And from Results conclusion could be drawn.

In the Excel sheet we input the following data in table-1

Item Type-SL. No	
Publication Year	
Search Engine	
Journal or Book name.	
Search Strings	
Author Name	
Title	
Publication Title	
Issue	
Volume	
Abstract	
Key Words	
Methodology	

Sample Size	
STUDY Area	
Result	
Conclusion	
Paper Publication	
Citation	

- a screening/selection procedure
- What is cloning method?
- Cloning is a technique scientists use to make exact genetic copies of living things. Genes, cells, tissues, and even whole animals can all be cloned. Some clones already exist in nature.

The three models for DNA replication

- Conservative. Replication produces one helix made entirely of old DNA and one helix made entirely of new DNA.
- Semi-conservative. Replication produces two helices that contain one old and one new DNA strand.
- Dispersive.
- What is an example of DNA replication?

Replication

is the process by which a cell copies its DNA prior to division. In humans, for example, each parent cell must copy its entire six billion base pairs of DNA before undergoing mitosis.

DNA CLONING (Figure-11)

What are the 4 steps in cloning? (A Theoretical Methodology Discussion):

In the classical restriction enzyme digestion and ligation cloning protocols, cloning of any DNA fragment essentially involves four steps:

- isolation of the DNA of interest (or target DNA),
- ligation,
- Transfect ion (or transformation), and.

Uses of DNA Clone

In basic research labs, biologists often use DNA cloning to build artificial, recombinant versions of genes that help them understand how normal genes in an organism function.

Why use PCR for cloning?

PCR cloning is a rapid method for cloning genes, and is often used for projects that require higher throughput than traditional cloning methods can accommodate. It allows for the cloning of DNA fragments that are not available in large amounts.

Innovative Objectives on Folding and Attachments of DNA/RNA

Changing targeting molecules we can enhance or decrease the folding types or pattern. Present studies predicts that as per stability of the molecules, transition states and activation energy KCP (Kinetically Controlled Product) or TCP (Thermodynamically Controlled Product) find there routs.

Changing solvent/temperature may also effect on structure folding.

We have to synthesise those structures those are useful tools for drug design or protein repairing for cloning purposes.

Update of Research design by software

- Molecular docking tools like CDHIT, Auto dock Vina in the work of Bioinformatics
- Use of Protein /Ligand DATA Bank (PDB software), Avogadro, PubChem etc.
- chemspider in the chemical drawing and structural analysis
- Use of AI-Artificial Drug design Intelligence for drug design and other.

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The topological diversity of DNA stems from supra molecular chemistry considerations: nucleobases (A, C, G, T) associate through the formation of hydrogen bonds (H-bonds), two in the A T base pair, three in the G C base pair, allowing for a dynamic assembly/disassembly without substantial energy penalty. However, nucleobases are not exclusive in their H-bond-mediated association, and >20 different pairing modes are possible involving two of the four letters (31), offering

Figure-12(H Bonding in DNA)

The canonical, so called Watson–Crick, structure is referred to as B-DNA (as the X-ray crystallographic structure was obtained by Rosalind Franklin after hydration of a first sample ('A') of high-quality DNA provided by Rudolf categorized as a non-B-DNA structure, spanning from A-DNA (thus, dehydrated duplex) (11) to Z-DNA (duplex of inverted helicity, Z for zigzag) (10,15).

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before being characterized in DNA in 1979; (22) the G-quartet in 1962 (23), the constitutive unit of the quadruple helix G-quadruple (G4-DNA, or G-DNA)

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The reason why these alternative structures have been overlooked for years is that their existence in a cellular context is challenged by the chromatin environment, in which the dense DNA packaging massively favors B-DNA. This has made the demonstration of their existence in vivo-like conditions daunting, and the chemical biology tools required to do so have reached the necessary degree of maturity only recently (e.g. the visualization of G4s in fixed cells by the antibody BG4 in 2013 (35), in live cells by the small molecule SiR-PyPDS in 2020) (36).

Also, the rules that dictate their formation in the genome are poorly understood even if the sequences these structures fold from (i.e. repeated sequences) are known to be both abundant and widespread in the human genome (repetitive DNA elements cover roughly half of our genome) (37,38).

Non-B-DNA- prone sequences can be inverted repeats (IR, involved in the formation of four-way DNA junction (FWJ), or cruciform DNA, Figures 1 and 2A), direct repeats (DR, involved in the formation of three-way DNA junction (TWJ), also termed slipped-strand DNA, slipped DNA or S-DNA (39), Figures 1 and 2B), mirror repeats (MR, involved in the formation of H-DNA) (38,40,41), or short tandem repeats (STR, involved in the formation of hairpin DNA, G4-DNA and i- motif (iM or I-DNA, Figure 1) depending of the repeated motif) (42). Thanks to recent computational analyses of an entirely sequenced human genome, the abundance of the non-B-DNA-prone sequences can be calculated: it is established that the least abundant motif is MR, with ca. 70 000 occurrences (ca. 2/100 kb), while the most abundant motif, IR, has >6000000 occurrences (ca. 206/100 kb) (41). However, despite the abundance of sequences that could give rise to non-B-DNA structures, the timing and kinetics of their folding are still poorly understood. Also, this folding requires the involved sequences is to be freed from the duplex structures as shown in the pictorial form.

Constraint (i.e. open chromatin, damaged DNA), their formation is thus transient only and subjected to a permanent and careful surveillance by ad hoc enzymes (e.g. helices) (43), which make their formation even less likely. This thus explains why non-B-DNA structures have not been considered as reliable genetic elements (and targets) for years. Despite all these constraints, some of these structures (G4s, iMs) have been isolated and identified by sequencing methods. Efforts invested in vitro (that is, with purified DNA fragments) confirmed their widespread formation in the human genome (with >500 000 G4- (44) and iM-forming (45)

Sequences), but not only (46) (e.g. >25 000 G4- (47) antiiM-forming (48) sequences in plants) (49). Investigations performed in vivo distinctly highlighted the suppressive role of chromatin for non-B-DNA structure formation as only ca. 1% of the G4s detected in vitro (G4-seq) (44) were detected in vivo (G4 ChIP-seq) (50). More globally, a combination of foot printing experiments (KMnO₄/S1 nuclease) and genome-wide sequencing (ssDNA-seq) allowed to links DNA regions in

mammalian cells with non-B-DNA structures (C-, G-, H- and Z-DNA, ca. 20 000 motifs each) and then, these structures with regions involved in gene expression regulation (51). Further combining nuclease cleavage (S1 and P1) and sequencing (S1-END-seq and P1-END-seq, respectively) revealed that C- and H-DNA formation (at dinucleotide (TA)_n repeats and hPu/hPy repeats (e.g. (GAA)_n, respectively) is both widespread in human cells but also strongly dependent on the cell status (cancerous versus non-cancerous cells) (52,53).

These results, beyond confirming the existence on non-B-DNA structures in vivo, provide also a strong correlation between structure-prone sequences and both mutability and genetic instability (52) (often referred to as to RIM, for repeat-induced mutagenesis) (54,55). Indeed, their widespread and no uniform distribution across our genome is significantly enriched in regulatory regions, and the distribution quite often overlaps with that of reported hotspots, i.e. regions prone to undergo breakage, deletions and translocations (38,41,55,56). This explains why repeated sequences are carefully patrolled and tightly controlled by genome surveillance systems, notably the DNA damage response (DDR) machinery (57–59).

As indicated above, to adopt higher-order structures, these sequences must be relieved from their duplex constraint and re annealed with misalignment or slippage. Their folding is thus dependent on, and coupled with, DNA trans- actions (transcription, replication) and repair. This makes them interesting targets for therapeutic approaches aimed at inflicting damage to highly active, that is, rapidly dividing cells. Indeed, once folded, these thermodynamically stable structures might act as roadblocks to polymerases, pausing and/or stalling their processivity, which is recognized as a situation of crisis (DNA damage) (60–63).

It is therefore unsurprising that chemical biologists soon envisioned an original strategy in which the transient stabilization of non- B-DNA structures by small molecules (so called ligands) could be exploited to foster this situation of crisis notably in rapidly dividing, that is, cancer cells (62,64). The

relevance of this approach is further substantiated by the fact that cancer cells are generally DDR-impaired (57), which makes them more sensitive to DNA damage-inducing agents than healthy cells. This explains why many of the therapeutics currently used in the clinic damage DNA, although through different modalities (65). However, these therapeutics target B-DNA (or their associated proteins such as topoisomerases) but none of them target non-B-DNA structures. This is clearly the major caveat of this field, which deserves to be addressed soon in order to lend credence to its strategic relevance.

The most advanced molecule, the G4-stabilizer CX-5461 is currently in phase I (clinicaltrials.gov NCT02719977) (66) against advanced solid tumors (its parent molecule CX-3543, also known as Quarfloxin, was stopped after phase I). Without a successful example of non-B-DNA targeting agent in the clinic, this field will keep on suffering from a lack of legitimacy. Yet, in contrary to B-DNA, which offers poorly defined binding sites only (i.e. minor and major grooves, intercalation in between 2 bp), non-B-DNA structures offer a broad variety of structurally well-defined ligand binding sites, which makes highly selective targeting with small molecules possible. Chief among them are the G4-DNA (67–69), which display two G-quartets surrounded by flexible loops, and DNA junctions (70–72),

in which the junction point between the duplex arms (3 duplex arms for TWJ; four arms for FWJ) creates a cavity prone to welcome small molecules (vide infra). The recent developments described in this review will be focused on the targeting of DNA junctions, as that of G4-DNA is regularly covered by authoritative reviews (68,69,73–77) to which interested readers are invited to refer. These developments offer this field a shining message of hope, as these new ligands allow for a specific targeting of DNA junctions (78), yet in vitro and cell-based assays only to date, which bears significant potential for delivering soon a new generation non-B-DNA targeting therapeutics for which the demonstration of clinical efficacy is greatly expected.

(FIGURE-13,FWJ,TWJ)

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VI. CONCLUSION

DNA quadruplexes, with their unique folding patterns and versatile applications, offer solutions to biomedical, technological, and environmental challenges. Their role in therapeutics, nanotechnology, and biosensing directly supports several SDGs, making them integral to future scientific and technological innovations.

Brief Conclusion from Small molecule (targeting Agents) addition with DNA/RNA

Targeting higher-order DNA structures with Adhoc ligands for chemical biology and/or medicinal chemistry purposes are now a commonly accepted strategy in drug design.

Folding of DNA/ RNA structure as per need in genetic modification to develop GMO.

Cloning of DNA/RNA for treatment of various diseases as per treatment of various diseases. The four natural DNA bases A-Adenosine, T-Thymine, G-Guanine, C-Cytosine are associated in base pairs as (A=T and G≡C), allowing the attached DNA strands to assemble into the canonical double helix of DNA which is duplex of DNA, also known as B-DNA. The intrinsic supra molecular properties of nuclei bases make other associations possible such as base triplets or quartets, which thus translates into a diversity of DNA structures is ripe with approximately 20 letters, (from A- to Z-DNA); however, only a few of them are being considered as key players in cell biology and by extension, valuable targets for chemical biology invention. In the present review, we summarise (1) what is known about alternative DNA structures (2) what are they? (3) When, where and how they fold?

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For example to find Structural Modification/Geometrical changes by DNA Quadruples Folding are done by attachment of second prototypes of ligands. DNA quadruples participate in many biological functions. It takes up a variety of folds based on the sequence and environment. Here, a meticulous analysis of experimentally determined 437 quadruple structures (433 PDBs) deposited in the PDB is carried out.

The analysis reveals the modular representation of the quadruples folds. Forty-eight unique quadruple motifs (whose diversity arises out of the propeller, bulge, diagonal, and lateral loops that connect the quartets) are identified, leading to simple to complex inter/intra molecular quadruple folds. The two-layered structural motifs are further classified into 33 continuous and 15 discontinuous motifs. While the continuous motifs can directly be extended to a quadruple fold; the discontinuous motif requires an additional loop(s) to complete a fold, as illustrated here with examples. Similarly, higher-order quadruple folds can also be represented by continuous or discontinuous motifs or their combinations.

In order to achieve Sustainable Development Goals we have to get maximum stable form of folding to get both thermodynamically and kinetically stable DNA or RNA structure to get proper drug design for the treatment of target diseases or cloning purposes. Help of molecular docking software like AutodocVina and help of PDB software we have to perform it. Alternatively applied those drugs to the victim like Rabbits or mouses etc. for a time period for particular target diseases for optimal treatment result conditions. The topic is under the domain of modern Analytical Chemistry and biotechnology up gradation purposes. With attachment of small molecules with DNA/RNA Finding proper cloning or staled DNA folding and to find optimal drug design for the treatment of target disease and to find a diseases free society for lifelong initiatives.

Such a modular representation of the quadruple folds may assist in custom engineering of quadruples, designing motif-based drugs, and the

prediction of the quadruple structure. Furthermore, it could facilitate understanding of the role of quadruples' in biological functions and diseases.

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REFERENCE

1. Hoshika, S., Leal, N.A., Kim, M.-J., Kim, M.-S., Karalkar, N.B., Kim, H.-J., Bates, A.M., Watkins, N.E., Santa Lucia, H.A., Meyer, A.J. et al. (2019) Hachimoji DNA and RNA: a genetic system with eight building blocks. *Science*, 363, 884–887.
2. Kirnos, M.D., Khudyakov, I.Y., Alexandrushkina, N.I. and Vanyushin, B.F. (1977) 2-Amino adenine is an adenine substituting for a base in S-2L cyanophage DNA. *Nature*, 270, 369–370.
3. Pezo, V., Jaziri, F., Bourguignon, P.-Y., Louis, D., Jacobs-Sera, D., Rozenski, J., Pochet, S., Herdewijn, P., Hatfull, G.F., Kaminski, P.-A. et al. (2021) Noncanonical DNA polymerization by amino adenine-based siphoviruses. *Science*, 372, 520–524.
4. Sleiman, D., Garcia, P.S., Lagune, M., Loc'h, J., Haouz, A., Taib, N., Rothlisberger, P., Gribaldo, S., Marlière, P. and Kaminski, P.A. (2021) A third purine biosynthetic pathway encoded by amino adenine-based viral DNA genomes. *Science*, 372, 516–520.
5. Zhou, Y., Xu, X., Wei, Y., Cheng, Y., Guo, Y., Khudyakov, I., Liu, F., He, P., Song, Z., Li, Z. et al. (2021) A widespread pathway for substitution of adenine by diaminopurine in phage genomes. *Science*, 372, 512–516.
7. Ghosh, A. and Bansal, M. (2003) a glossary of DNA structures from A to Z. *Acta Crystallography. D: Biol. Crystallography.*, 59, 620–626.
8. Franklin, R.E. and Gosling, R.G. (1953) The structure of sodium thymonucleate fibres. I. The influence of water content. *Acta Crystallography.* 6, 673–677.
9. Franklin, R.E. and Gosling, R.G. (1953) Evidence for 2-chain helix in crystalline structure of sodium deoxyribonucleate. *Nature*, 172, 156–157.
10. Franklin, R.E. and Gosling, R.G. (1953) Molecular configuration in sodium thymonucleate. *Nature*, 171, 740–741.
11. Elkin, L.O. (2003) Rosalind franklin and the double helix. *Physics Today*, 56, 42–48.
12. Ravichandran, S., Subramanian, V.K. and Kim, K.K. (2019) Z-DNA in the genome: from structure to disease. *Biophysics. Rev.*, 11, 383–387.
13. Crick, F.H. (1958) on protein synthesis. *Symp. Soc. Exp. Biol.*, 12, 138–163.
14. Crick. (1970) Central dogma of molecular biology. *Nature*, 227, 561.
15. Wilkins, M.H.F., Stokes, A.R. and Wilson, H.R. (1953) Molecular structure of nucleic acids: molecular structure of deoxypentose nucleic acids. *Nature*, 171, 738–740.
16. Dalla Pozza, M., Abdullrahman, A., Cardin, C.J., Gasser, G. and Hall, J.P. (2022) Three's a crowd stabilization, structure, and applications of DNA triplexes. *Chem. Sci.*, 13, 10193–10215.
17. Htun, H. and Dahlberg, J.E. (1989) Topology and formation of triple-stranded H-DNA. *Science*, 243, 1571–1576.
18. Felsenfeld, G., Davies, D.R. and Rich, A. (1957) Formation of a three-stranded polynucleotide molecule. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 79, 2023–2024.
19. Lee, J.S., Johnson, D.A. and Morgan, A.R. (1979) Complexes formed by (pyrimidine)_n (purine)_n DNAs on lowering the pH are Three-stranded. *Nucleic Acids Res.*, 6, 3073–3091.
20. Gellert, M., Lipsett, M.N. and Davies, R.D. (1962) Helix formation by guanylic acid. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U*

21. Panayotatos, N. and Wells, R.D. (1981) Cruciform structures in supercoiled DNA. *Nature*, 289, 466–470.
22. Pohl, F.M. (1967) Ein modeler DNS-Structure. *Naturwissenschaften*, 54, 616–616.
23. Wang, A.H.J., Quigley, G.J., Kolpak, F.J., Crawford, J.L., van Boom, J.H., van der Marel, G. and Rich, A. (1979) Molecular structure of a left-handed double helical DNA fragment at atomic resolution. *Nature*, 282, 680–686.
24. Sivakova, S. and Rowan, S.J. (2005) Nucleobases as supramolecular motifs. *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 34, 9–21.
25. Hoogsteen, K. (1959) The structure of crystals containing a hydrogen-bonded complex of 1-methylthymine and 9-methyladenine. *Acta Crystallography*. 12, 822–823.
26. Hoogsteen, K.R. (1963) The crystal and molecular structure of a hydrogen-bonded complex between 1-methylthymine and 9-methyladenine. *Acta Crystallography.*, 16, 907–916.
27. Arnott, S. and Bond, P.J. (1973) Structures for Poly(U).poly(A).poly(U) triple stranded polynucleotides. *Nat. New Biol.*, 244, 99–101.
28. Biffi, G., Tannahill, D., McCafferty, J. and Balasubramanian, S. (2013) Quantitative visualization of DNA G-quadruple structures in human cells. *Nat. Chem.*, 5, 182–186.
29. Di Antonio, M., Ponjavic, A., Radzevičius, A., Ranasinghe, R.T., Catalano, M., Zhang, X., Shen, J., Needham, L.-M., Lee, S.F., Klenerman, D. et al. (2020) Single-molecule visualization of DNA G-quadruple formation in live cells. *Nat. Chem.*, 12, 832–837.
30. Treangen, T.J. and Salzberg, S.L. (2012) Repetitive DNA and next-generation sequencing: computational challenges and solutions. *Nat. Rev. Genet.*, 13, 36–46.
31. Wang, G. and Vasquez, K.M. (2006) Non-B DNA structure-induced genetic instability. *Mutat. Res.*, 598, 103–119.
32. Pearson, C.E. and Sinden, R.R. (1996) Alternative structures in duplex DNA formed within the trinucleotide repeats of the myotonic dystrophy and fragile x loci. *Biochem.*, 35, 5041–5053.
33. Wells, R.D. (2007) Non-B DNA conformations, mutagenesis and disease. *Trends Biochem. Sci.*, 32, 271–278.
34. Georgakopoulos-Soares, I., Morganella, S., Jain, N., Hemberg, M. and Nik-Zainal, S. (2018) Noncanonical secondary structures arising from non-B DNA motifs are determinants of mutagenesis. *Genome Res.*, 28, 1264–1271.
35. Murat, P., Guilbaud, G. and Sale, J.E. (2020) DNA polymerase stalling at structured DNA constrains the expansion of short tandem repeats. *Genome Biol.*, 21, 209.
36. Singleton, M.R., Dillingham, M.S. and Wigley, D.B. (2007) Structure and mechanism of helicases and nucleic acid translocators. *Annu. Rev. Biochem.*, 76, 23–50.
37. Chambers, V.S., Marsico, G., Boutell, J.M., Di Antonio, M., Smith, G.P. and Balasubramanian, S. (2015) High-throughput sequencing of DNA G-quadruple structures in the human genome. *Nat. Biotechnology.*, 33, 877–881.
38. Peña Martínez, C.D., Zeraati, M., Rouet, R., Mazigi, O., Gloss, B., Chan, C.-L., Bryan, T.M., Smith, N.M., Dinger, M.E., Kummerfeld, S. et al. (2022) Human genomic DNA is widely interspersed with I-motif structures. *BioRxiv* doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.04.14.488274>, 14 April 2022, preprint: not peer reviewed.
39. Marsico, G., Chambers, V.S., Sahakyan, A.B., McCauley, P., Boutell, J.M., Antonio, M.D. and Balasubramanian, S. (2019) Whole genome experimental maps of DNA G-quadruples in multiple species. *Nucleic Acids Res.*, 47, 3862–3874.
40. Feng, Y., Tao, S., Zhang, P., Rota Sperti, F., Liu, G., Cheng, X., Zhang, T., Yu, H., Wang, X., Chen, C. et al. (2022) Epigenomic features of DNA G-quadruplexes and their roles in regulating rice gene transcription. *Plant Physiol.*, 188, 1632–1648
Ma, X., Feng, Y., Yang, Y., Li, X., Shi, Y., Tao, S., Cheng, X., Huang, J.,
41. Wang, X., Chen, C. et al. (2022) Genome-wide characterization of i-motifs and their potential roles in the stability and evolution of transposable elements in rice. *Nucleic Acids Res.*, 50, 3226–3238.

42. Li, M., Tian, R., Monchaud, D. and Zhang, W. (2022) Omics studies of DNA G-/C-quadruplexes in plants. *Trends Genet.*, 38, 999–1002.
43. Hañsel-Hertsch, R., Beraldi, D., Lensing, S.V., Marsico, G., Zyner, K., Parry, A., Di Antonio, M., Pike, J., Kimura, H. and Narita, M. (2016) G-quadruplex structures mark human regulatory chromatin. *Nat. Genet.*, 48, 1267–1272.
44. Kouzine, F., Wojtowicz, D., Baranello, L., Yamane, A., Nelson, S., Resch, W., Kieffer-Kwon, K.-R., Benham, C.J., Casellas, R., Przytycka, T.M. et al. (2017) Permanganate/S1 nuclease foot printing reveals Non-B DNA structures with regulatory potential across a mammalian genome. *Cell Syst.*, 4, 344–356.
45. van Wietmarschen, N., Sridharan, S., Nathan, W.J., Tubbs, A., Chan, E.M., Callen, E., Wu, W., Belinky, F., Tripathi, V., Wong, N. et al. (2020) Repeat expansions confer WRN dependence in microsatellite-unstable cancers. *Nature*, 586, 292–298.
46. Matos-Rodrigues, G., van Wietmarschen, N., Wu, W., Tripathi, V., Koussa, N.C., Pavani, R., Nathan, W.J., Callen, E., Belinky, F., Mohammed, A. et al. (2022) S1-END-seq reveals DNA secondary structures in human cells. *Mol. Cell*, 82, 3538–3552.
47. Shah, K.A., Shishkin, A.A., Voineagu, I., Pavlov, Y.I., Shcherbakova, P.V. and Mirkin, S.M. (2012) Role of DNA polymerases in repeat-mediated genome instability. *Cell Rep.*, 2, 1088–1095.
48. Shah, K.A. and Mirkin, S.M. (2015) The hidden side of unstable DNA repeats: mutagenesis at a distance. *DNA Repair*, 32, 106–112.
49. Wang, G. and Vasquez, K.M. (2014) Impact of alternative DNA structures on DNA damage, DNA repair, and genetic instability. *DNA Repair*, 19, 143–151.
50. Jackson, S.P. and Bartek, J. (2009) The DNA-damage response in human biology and disease. *Nature*, 461, 1071–1078.
51. Ciccia, A. and Elledge, S.J. (2010) The DNA damage response: making it safe to play with knives. *Mol. Cell*, 40, 179–204.
52. Blackford, A.N. and Jackson, S.P. (2017) ATM, ATR, and DNA-PK: the trinity at the heart of the DNA damage response. *Mol. Cell*, 66, 801–817.
53. Mirkin, E.V. and Mirkin, S.M. (2007) Replication fork stalling at natural impediments. *Microbiol. Mol. Biol. Rev.*, 71, 13–35.
54. Belotserkovskii, B.P., Mirkin, S.M. and Hanawalt, P.C. (2013) DNA sequences that interfere with transcription: implications for genome function and stability. *Chem. Rev.*, 113, 8620–8637.
55. Zell, Rota Sperti, F., Britton, S. and Monchaud, D. (2021) DNA folds threaten genetic stability and can be leveraged for chemotherapy. *RSC Chem. Biol.*, 2, 47–76.
56. Kaushal, S. and Freudenreich, C.H. (2019) The role of fork stalling and DNA structures in causing chromosome fragility. *Genes Chromosomes Cancer*, 58, 270–283.
57. Del Mundo, I.M., Vasquez, K.M. and Wang, G. (2019) Modulation of DNA structure formation using small molecules. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta - Mol. Cell Res.*, 1866, 118539.
58. Roos, W.P., Thomas, A.D. and Kaina, B. (2016) DNA damage and the balance between survival and death in cancer biology. *Nat. Rev. Cancer*, 16, 20–33.
59. Hilton, J., Gelmon, K., Bedard, P.L., Tu, D., Xu, H., Tinker, A.V., Goodwin, R., Laurie, S.A., Jonker, D., Hansen, A.R. et al. (2022) Results of the phase I CCTG IND.231 trial of CX-5461 in patients with advanced solid tumors enriched for DNA-repair deficiencies. *Nat. Commun.*, 13, 3607.
60. Burge, S., Parkinson, G.N., Hazel, P., Todd, A.K. and Neidle, S. (2006) Quadruplex DNA: sequence, topology and structure. *Nucleic Acids Res.*, 34, 5402–5415.
61. Rhodes, D. and Lipps, H.J. (2015) G-quadruplexes and their regulatory roles in biology. *Nucleic Acids Res.*, 43, 8627–8637.
62. Varshney, D., Spiegel, J., Zyner, K., Tannahill, D. and Balasubramanian, S. (2020) The regulation and functions of DNA and RNA G-quadruplexes. *Nat. Rev. Mol. Cell Biol.*, 21, 459–474.
63. Lilley, D.M. (2000) Structures of helical junctions in nucleic acids. *Q. Rev. Biophys.*, 33, 109–159.
64. Altona, C. (1996) Classification of nucleic acid junctions. *J. Mol. Biol.*, 263, 56.